

Studies on Metal Chelates with Polydentate Ligands

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The Schiff's base, bis-salicylaldehyde-triethylenetetramine, has been shown to provide stable compounds with Co^{3+} , Co^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Al^{3+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , and the ions of other transitional metals in which the reagent serves as a polydentate ligand¹. In view of the interesting properties of the chelating agent, it is considered worthwhile to prepare a chelating agent of the similar type and compare the properties of the new chelates with those of the former. With this end in view, the oxygenated bis-salicylaldehyde-triethylenetetramine, i.e. bis-salicyl-triethylenetetramine (I), has been prepared.

Methyl salicylate and triethylenetetramine were mixed together in 2:1 molar ratio and heated on a water bath. The resulting semisolid mass was extracted with rectified spirit and the extract poured into water when white needle-shaped crystals separated. The product was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. The substance is insoluble in water but highly soluble in ethanol, acetone, etc. The air-dried substance on analysis corresponds to the formula: $\text{RH}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, where RH_2 = one molecule of the reagent (I). (Found: C, 48.87; H, 7.65, N, 11.86; H_2O , 21.78. Calc. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4$, $6\text{H}_2\text{O}$: C, 48.59; H, 7.69; N, 11.33; H_2O , 21.86%.)

It is evident from the structure of the oxygenated Schiff's base that it can behave both as a diacidic base and dibasic acid forming salts of the compositions: $\text{RH}_2 \cdot 2\text{HCl}$ and Na_2R .

The four acid dissociation constants have been determined by titrating the dihydrochloride with alkali, following the method of Bjerrum². The equations may be represented as:

(where $\text{RH}_2 = \text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$). The four pK values are $pK_1 = 9.78$, $pK_2 = 8.79$, $pK_3 = 7.73$, and $pK_4 = 4.99$.

1. Das Sharma and Bailar, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 5476.

2. Bjerrum, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solutions", P. Haas and Sons, Copenhagen, 1941.

The reagent serves as a polydentate ligand and provides stable complexes with Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , etc.

Copper Compound.—The copper (II) compound was isolated by mixing together an ethanolic solution of the reagent and copper acetate (1:1). From the solution copper compound separated as pink, needle-shaped crystals. The product was recrystallised from ethanol. The magnetic susceptibility measurement for copper compound has been found to be 1.79. B.M. {Found: Cu, 13.46; N, 11.76. Calc. for $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4)] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$: Cu, 13.56; N, 12.02%}.

Nickel Compound.—The nickel (II) chelate was prepared in an analogous method. It is diamagnetic, suggesting a planar configuration with dsp^2 bonds. It is an orange crystalline compound. {Found: C, 53.36; H, 5.32; N, 12.28; Ni, 13.22. Calc. for $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4)]$: C, 54.21; H, 5.42; N, 12.65; Ni, 13.26}.

The formation of metal chelates of bivalent and trivalent metal ions in solutions has been studied by Bjerrum's method^{2,3} and the stability of the complexes has been determined. The stability order for trivalent metal was found as: $\text{Fe}^{3+} > \text{Al}^{3+} > \text{Cr}^{3+} > \text{Y}^{3+}$ and for bivalent metals: $\text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+} > \text{Cd}^{2+}$, the formation of Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} compounds being very negligible. Further work and isolation of trivalent metal chelates are in progress. Details of the work will be published later.

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